

NDAC/LO/065

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14th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm)

The software package for simulating IDT counts was further developed by including phase distortion by the IFOV. The analysis program, in which the astrometric parameters and binary data are estimated by least-squares, has been run on a large number of simulated cases in order to study the astrometric errors and their dependence on separation and magnitude difference and the mode of observation (e.g. pointing towards photocentre versus alternating between components).

The errors are generally surprisingly small, also for pairs in the 'critical' region, i.e. with small magnitude difference and separations in the range 5 to 25 arcsec. Based on these findings we have made a recommendation to the INCA Consortium not to exclude known double stars by an *a priori* rule, as was previously the idea.

The binary solutions thus far have assumed a certain prior information on the location of the components, eliminating the need for more elaborate search techniques and application of significance tests. These problems will be attacked in the spring-summer 1986 (see revised bar chart, issue No. 4).

Miscellaneous

A mathematical formulation of the TYCHO astrometry task was written (C ). The activities of the Data Reduction Consortia (NDAC, FAST) were presented by Lindegren and Kovalevsky at a joint meeting of Commissions 7, 8, 24, 25, 33, and 37 on the HIPPARCOS project at the IAU General Assembly in Delhi.

Working paper

C Lindegren 1985 Sept 3: TYCHO Astrometry - Mathematical Formulation